

CIRCULAR SPRINT 2021 – GENERAL TERMS AND CONDITIONS

1. General

Aalto university (“Aalto”), Gent University (“UGent”), and Clausthal University of Technology (“TU Clausthal”) are partners in the EIT RawMaterials funded project CRAFTH: CiRcular design & manuFacTuring Hackathon between 1.1.-31.12.2021(hereinafter “Project”). These three partners, hereinafter “Organizers” will arrange the Circular Sprint event (hereinafter “Design Sprint”) as part of the Project.

The term “Design Sprint” means an event where participants solve challenges set by the Organizers and their partners over a fixed period of time. Companies participating to the Design Sprint (“Companies”) will provide challenges or problems (“Challenges”) to the Design Sprint for the Participants to solve.

You are registering as participant (“Participant”) to the Design Sprint. By registering Participant accepts and is committed to these terms and conditions and to all further guidance and instructions given by the Organizer related to the Design Sprint. These terms constitute a binding legal agreement between Participant and the Organizer.

2. Participation to the Design Sprint

The Organizers will arrange the Design Sprint between 7.-17.9.2021. The Design Sprint is a two-week program where registered Participants are divided into teams by the Organizers. On the first week, Participants attend online educational lectures and team activities provided by the Project partners. The second week the Participant teams will engage in design sprint activities with an objective to solve or develop solutions for the Challenges provided by the Companies. The second week includes physical prototyping at the dedicated Organizer premises. Online participation is made possible also during the second week if discussed with the Organizers when registering to the Design Sprint.

The Organizers are responsible for general planning, preparations and execution of the Design Sprint together with the Project consortium and the Company. When registering to the Design Sprint, Participant is obligated to provide the Organizers accurate and complete information. Organizers may at their own decision provide prizes to Participants but are not obligated to do so.

Organizers reserve right to check the Participants after registration and disclose them from the Design Sprint if they see it necessary for safety or other reasons.

For the clarity it is mentioned that Organizers will not be held responsible and cover costs and expenses that result to the Participant from participating to Design Sprint, including but not limited to travel costs, accommodation, food costs.

During the Design Sprint Participants will use the material provided to them to solely to solve the Challenges according to instructions given to them. Participant will not

cause any harm to the Organizer, its premises, software or other property, to Companies, other Participants or to any third party.

The Design Sprint is based on teamwork. Thus, Participants are required to attend the online lectures, all team activities, and design sprint activities scheduled by the Organizers to the best of their ability and schedule. Personal force majeure situations that prevent participation for individual activities are accepted as long as their amount is low, and they have been clearly communicated with the Organizer when registering for the Design Sprint or at the time of occurrence.

When participating to the Design Sprint, Participant:

- will not violate any applicable law, violate any IPR, business secrets, or privacy of third parties
- transmit any unauthorized advertising, promotional materials, junk mail, spam, chain letters, contests, pyramid schemes, or any other form of solicitation or mass messaging;
- transmit any material that contains adware, malware, spyware, software viruses, worms or any other computer code designed to interrupt, destroy, or limit the functionality of computer software or equipment.
- cause any other kind of damage to any stakeholder of Circular Sprint

If Participant is provided access to the Organizer's premises, software or other property, they will be obligated to follow all instructions given to them related to said use. Participant will not cause any harm to those premises, software or property.

If Participant violates these terms and conditions, the Organizer has the right to disqualify the breaching Participant from the Design Sprint.

3. Intellectual property rights

Intellectual Property Rights (hereinafter IPR) mean all forms of intellectual property protection, including patents, utility models, trademarks, copyrights, chip topography rights, design rights (including unregistered design rights), as well as know-how and applications for the same.

All material provided by the Organizer or Companies to the Design Sprint are owned by them. Participants are granted non-exclusive, limited right to use provided material to solve the Challenges during the Design Sprint. User right to said material terminates when the Design Sprint ends.

All material and results generated by Participants will be solely owned by them. Organizer or Companies make no claims to any intellectual property, material or results generated by the Participants during the Design Sprint if not other ways stated in these terms and conditions.

4. Participant material

Participant will be solely responsible for the IPR, content, results and material ("Material") they will provide to and in the Design Sprint. Participant shall at all times ensure that Participant's Material does not infringe any rights of third parties or any applicable law. The Material provided by Participant shall not be offensive, threatening, libelous, defamatory or otherwise inappropriate. Organizer is not responsible and shall not be held liable for any such Material, nor do they endorse any opinion contained in Material or content of the Participants.

If Material provided by Participant is against these terms, Organizer is entitled to delete such material and possibly disqualify the Participant from the Design Sprint.

The Organizer will not backup the Participant Material.

5. Publicity

Design Sprint is a public event. By participating in the Design Sprint, Participant acknowledges that the Design Sprint will be recorded, filmed and/or photographed for reference and similar use, and therefore you grant the Organizer a worldwide, perpetual, irrevocable, sublicensable and non-exclusive license to display your work performed at the Design Sprint for promotional and marketing purposes of the Organizer. Furthermore, Participant consents to any such footage to be published in Organizer's and/or a third party's, as the case may be, marketing and communication channels without the Participant's review or approval. You understand that you will not receive any royalty or compensation for this use of your work by Organizer.

By participating to Design Sprint, Participant grants Organizers a worldwide, perpetual, irrevocable, sublicensable and non-exclusive license to display your Material and results generated in the Design Sprint for scientific publications and for marketing purposes. Furthermore, Participant consents to any such footage to be published in Organizer's and/or a third party's, as the case may be, marketing and communication channels without the Participant's review or approval. You understand that you will not receive any royalty or compensation for this use of your work by Organizer.

6. Confidentiality

In the context of Design Sprint, The Organizer may disclose Confidential Information to the Participants as the Organizer deems appropriate and desirable.

All information received by a Participant from the Organizer, Project partners whether orally, in writing, or in electronic or any other form shall be deemed confidential provided, that such information is clearly marked as confidential. The Party disclosing oral information intended as confidential information shall, at the time of disclosure, state that the information is confidential and within fourteen (14) days provide confirmation in writing of its confidential nature (hereinafter 'Confidential Information').

Participants undertake to treat Confidential Information confidential, undertake not to disclose Confidential Information to third parties and undertake not to use Confidential Information for purposes other than the fulfilment of their rights and obligations under this Agreement.

The confidentiality obligation does not, however, apply to information that:

- (a) was in the public domain or generally available to the public at the time of disclosure,
- (b) has become part of the public domain or generally available to the public subsequent to disclosure of the Confidential Information through no fault of the Participant,
- (c) was known to the Participant before receiving the information from the disclosing Party,
- (d) was obtained from a third party without any confidentiality obligations,
- (e) has been developed independently or together with a third party without breach of the confidentiality obligations of this Agreement, or
- (f) has to be disclosed or made public under law or other statute or order of a court of law or other authority.

7. Use of personal data

The Organizer collects and processes data, including personal data, in relation to Participant's registrations or applications on the Design Sprint, application to or participation in the Design Sprint, such as Participant's contact details, other identification data and other information relating to the Design Sprint. Basis of the use of personal data is contract between Participant and the Organizer. All use of personal data is according to the respective Organizer's Privacy Policy.

Aalto University privacy policy can be found on Aalto's webpage:

<https://www.aalto.fi/en/services/privacy-notice>

"PDF: *Privacy notice for Aalto University communication and events (All Aalto units)*"

8. Term of the agreement

This Agreement come in force when Participant registers to the Design Sprint and will continue to be in force until the contractual obligations has been fulfilled, but no later than to 31.12.2021. Provisions of this Agreement intended to survive the termination or expiry of this Agreement shall do so.

9. Indemnify and hold harmless

Participant agrees to and does hereby indemnify, hold harmless and defend the Organizers and their governing board, officers, employees and agents from every claim or demand made and every cost, liability, loss, damage or expense, of any nature whatsoever, which may be incurred by reason of, or which may be directly or indirectly related to Participants actions.

10. Limitation of liability

The Organizer will use reasonable effort to arrange the Design Sprint and keep it operational. The Organizer reserves the right to change the content, timing, date or location of the Design Sprint, without liability to the Participant. The Organizer also reserves the right to cancel the Design Sprint at any time.

The Organizer shall not be liable for any direct, indirect or consequential damages or losses caused in the execution of the Agreement towards the other Participant. Indirect loss refers to damage caused by: the reduction or interruption in production or turnover; other loss arising because the results cannot be used as intended; loss of profit arising because a contract with a third party has been lost or breached; loss due to damage to property other than results, or other similar loss that is difficult to fore-see. Limitation of liability shall not apply to damages caused wilfully or due to gross negligence.

The Organizer is not liable for any delay or non-performance of its obligations due to force majeure. Any event, which prevents or renders the performance of the Agreement unreasonably difficult within the time specified, shall be considered force majeure. Such events include, but are not limited to, war, insurrection, epidemic, pandemic, natural disaster, interruption in the general energy supply, fire, strike, embargo, material restriction imposed by the government budget or by the government on the activities of the Organizer, the termination of employment, serious illness or accident of a person who is essential for the execution of the Agreement, or other equally significant and uncommon reason beyond a Party's control. A delay on the part of a subcontractor for the above reason shall also be deemed to constitute force majeure.

11. Governing law and disputes

All disputes relating to this Agreement (including disputes relating specifically to this clause) shall be governed by and construed in accordance with Finnish legislation without any regard to its principles and rules on conflict of laws. Both Parties have an obligation to try and reach an agreement before initiating any legal procedures. Should an agreement not be reached, the disagreement shall be settled in the District Court of Helsinki, Finland.

12. Entire agreement

This Agreement constitutes the entire agreement between the Parties with respect to the subject matter hereof and supersedes all prior agreements, proposals, undertakings, and other representations and communications between the Parties.

13. Miscellaneous

No party shall, without the prior written consent of the other Party, assign or transfer the Agreement in whole or in part to a third party.

If one or more of the provisions of this Agreement are found to be invalid, the validity, and enforceability of the remaining provisions of this Agreement shall not in any way be affected or impaired. The parties shall replace the invalid provision by a new provision that meets the intention of the parties when signing this Agreement.